

Biochemical Studies of Black Gram Seeds Infected with Seed-Borne Fungi

Jagat Pal Singh

Associate Professor, R. R. Govt. College, Alwar (Rajasthan)
Received: 22/07/2023; Accepted 22/08/2023; Published 25/10/2023

ABSTRACT

Pulses constitute important proteinaceous crops. Several Seed-borne fungi are known to cause considerable loss in the seed content. Black gram contains 59.6% carbohydrates. Black gram contains 59.6% carbohydrates. Faulty storage conditions make the seeds more vulnerable to fungal attack. Many researchers have reported marked decrease in protein contents.

Key words: Biochemical contents, seed-borne fungi, storage conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Pulses constitute important proteinaceous crops. Several Seed-borne fungi are known to cause considerable loss in the seed content. Bilgrami et. al. (1976) studied deterioration of black gram seed in storage conditions by *Aspergillus flavus*. They recorded loss in sugars and organic acid contents but a few amino acids and organic acids were found to be synthesized by *A. flavus*. Deterioration of proteins, total sugars and protein contents was also noted in black gram seeds during infestation by *A. flavus* in thirty eight cultivars of pulse crops by Premlata Singh, Sita Bhagat and Ahmed (1990). Ibraheem, Okesha and Mhathem (1987) reported marked decrease in protein contents of soybean seeds by associated seed-borne fungi. Contrary to this, an increase in protein contents in rice seeds due to helminthosporiose infection was reported by Vidhyasekaran et. al.(1973). Shukla et. al. (1988) recorded decrease in protein contents of Arhar seeds infested with different *Aspergilli*. The amount differed from species to species. *A. flavus* and *A. niger* brought maximum and *A. awamori* and *A. nidulans* minimum alterations in protein contents.

Black gram contains 59.6% carbohydrates. Bilgrami et. al. (1976) recorded disappearance of sugars within 5 days of incubation period. But it again appeared on the 10th and 15th days of incubation. Vidhyasekaran and Govindaswamy (1968) also observed the accumulation of reducing sugars due to seed-borne fungi in paddy seeds. Changes in starch contents of Arhar seeds by fungal infection was also studied by Sinha et. al. (1981). Maheshwari, Chaturvedi and Yadav (1984) observed depletion in starch contents of *Coriander sativum* infected with *Protomyces macrosporus*.

Faulty storage conditions make the seeds more vulnerable to fungal attack. Several storage fungi produce aflatoxins which cause great health hazards in human beings. Aflatoxin production in water soaked black gram seeds by four isolates of *A. flavus* was observed by Reddy and Subbaya (1985). Premlata et. al. (1990) screened thirty eight different pulse cultivars against aflatoxin production by *A. flavus*. Two cultivars were found highly resistant against aflatoxin elaboration. They also recorded greater amount of total phenol and proteins in resistant varieties than susceptible ones of the same pulse crop.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Important constituents of black gram seed viz. proteins, starch and total soluble sugars were studied in symptomatic seeds infected with *R. bataticola* and *F. oxysporum*. Standard biochemical techniques were followed for analysis. Healthy seeds were taken as control.

Extraction

100 mg of dry seed powder was extracted in 10 ml. of 80% ethanol and kept overnight. The extracted mass was centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant so obtained was used for estimation of total soluble sugars whereas the residue was collected for starch estimation.

Protein Estimation

Total soluble proteins were estimated by the method of Lowry, Rosebrough, Farr and Randale (1951). 100 mg of seed powder was mixed in 10 ml. of ethanol-ether (2:1, v/v) solution and was left overnight. It was centrifuged for 5 min. at 2500rpm, supernatant was discarded. The residue after drying was used for further extraction. Dried residue was mixed in 10 ml. of 10% TCA (Tri Carboxylic Acid), grinded properly and centrifuged for 5 min. Supernatant was discarded and residue was further treated by same practise. Later the residue was mixed with 10 ml. of 1N NaOH, boiled for 10 min, cooled aliquot was taken and mixed with 5 ml alkaline solution. To this 0.5 ml Folin reagent was added and shaken properly. After 30 min absorbance was taken on spectronic-20 spectrophotometer at 750 nm using filter. Alkaline solution was prepared by mixing Reagent B (0.5% copper sulphate in 1% sodium potassium tartarate). Standard curve was prepared by using Bovine Serum Albumin protein. Same method was employed and adopted for infected seeds.

Total Soluble Sugars Estimation

Total soluble sugars were estimated according to method as described by Dubbois, Giller, Hailton, Rebers and Smith (1951).

0.5 ml of supernatant per sample were taken and 1 ml of 5% phenol was added to this. To the final solution 5 ml of 96% sulphuric acid was rapidly mixed and allowed to cool under running tap water for 20 min. The optical density was determined at 490 nm. Reference curve was prepared by using glucose.

Starch Estimation

Starch contents were estimated by following the method of Mc Cready, Guggalzo, Silviera and Owens (1950). The residue was utilized for starch estimation. It was suspended in 5 ml of distilled water and subsequently 6.5 ml of 52% per chloric acid was added to this. The final volume was centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 30 min. This process was repeated for three times and the supernatant was collected and final volume was made 100 ml by adding deionised water. This mixture was filtered through Whatman filter paper no. 42. 0.5 ml of this filtrate was used for estimating starch contents by following the same method adopted for total soluble sugars. Starch contents were calculated by using conversion factor 0.9 to convert the values of glucose to starch.

RESULTS

Biochemical estimation of total soluble proteins, total soluble sugars and starch in healthy and *R. bataticola* and *F. oxysporum* infected seeds were carried out.

Total soluble proteins

The amount of protein was 211.3 mg / gm in healthy seeds whereas in *R. bataticola* and *F. oxysporum* infected seeds it was 233.6 and 215.0 mg / gm respectively. The increase was found insignificant.

Total soluble sugars

Not significant difference in sugar content was observed. The amount was 55.6 mg / gm in healthy seeds and 51.4 mg / gm in *R. bataticola* and 530.0 mg / gm in *F. oxysporum* infected seeds.

Starch

Starch was lower in infected seeds than the healthy ones but the difference was insignificant. It was recorded 518.20 mg / gm in healthy seeds whereas 510.00 mg / gm in *R. bataticola* and 486.52 mg / gm in *F. oxysporum* infected seeds.

Table -1 Amount mentioned in various metabolited of *R. bataticola* and *F. oxyporum*

Seeds	Metabolites (mg.gm) of dry weight*		
	Total soluble proteins	Total soluble sugars	Starch
Health seeds	211.3	55.6	518.20
<i>R. bataticola</i>	223.6	51.4	510.00
<i>F. oxyporum</i>	215.0	53.0	486.52
C.D. at 5% level	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bilgrami K S, Prasad T, Jammaluddin, and Roy A K 1976. Studies on the deterioration of some pulses by fungi. *Indian Phytopath* 29 374-377.
- [2]. Lowry O H, Rosenbrough N J, Farr A L and Randall R J 1951. Protein measurement with the Folin-phenol reagent. *J Biol Chem* 193 265-275.
- [3]. Premlata Singh, Sita Bhagat and Ahmed 1990. Aflatoxin elaboration and nutritional deterioration in some pulse cultivars during infestation with *Aspergillus flavus*. *J food Sci & Technol* 27(1) 60-62.
- [4]. Shukla H S, Dubey S Km and Tripathi S C 1988. Changes in protein contents of Arhar (*Cajanus cajan*) due to fungal association. *Legume Res* 11 (2) 85-88.
- [5]. Sinha M K, singh B K and Prasad T 1981. Changes in starch contents of Arhar seeds due to fungi. *Indian Phytopath* 34 269-271.
- [6]. Vidhysekaran P and Govindaswamy C V 1968. Role of seed-borne fungi in paddy spoilage. III. Production of carbon dioxide, fatty acids and reducing sugars. *Indian Phytopath Soc Bull* 4 71-78.
- [7]. Maheshwari D K, Chaturvedi S N and Yadav B S 1984. Qualitative and quantitative changes in starch and protein contents induced by *Protomyces macrosporus* in coriander stem. *Indian Phytopath* 37 170-173.